
African Traditional Antimalarials: A Review

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Abstract Traditional herbal medicines have been used to treat malaria for thousands of years in various parts of the world especially Africa. This review addresses medicinal plants used to treat malaria in traditional medicine from many Africa countries and compare popularly used native species, antimalarial activity of extracts and isolated substances. New drugs have to be developed to replace those compromised by parasite resistance. The identification of novel anti-malaria pharmacophores requires the scientific evaluation of relevant medicinal plants used in traditional health care.

Keywords Africa, medicinal plants, traditional antimalarial, *Plasmodium falciparum*

Introduction

Malaria remains a major public health problem in the world and Africa is said to be having the highest burden of malaria, this is due to the fact that *Plasmodium falciparum* (which is the most deadliest specie) occurs more in Africa and have led to an increased mortality rate (of about 600,000 deaths yearly) as well as morbidity [1]. It has been estimated that out of the over one million deaths caused by malaria world-wide, 90% occur in sub-Saharan Africa [2]. It is a public health problem of global concern because of its high economic burden on the nation, high prevalence of mortality in children, pregnant women and non-immune individuals [3]. The rapid increase of resistance to most of the available antimalarial drugs, as well as resistance of vectors to insecticides [4] led to the reemergence of malaria in many parts of the world. Drug resistant strains of *P. falciparum* have been found in many endemic areas of the world and the well-known chloroquine (CQ) and antifolates [sulfadoxine-pyrimethamine (S/P)] have been associated with treatment failure. This is also compounded by the difficulty of creating efficient vaccines and also adverse side-effects of the existing antimalarial drugs, this highlights the urgent need for novel, well-tolerated antimalarial drugs [5] for both prophylaxis and treatment of malaria. Plant-derived compounds played crucial roles in drug discovery and development for the treatment of malaria, the isolation of new bioactive compounds from medicinal plants based on traditional use or ethnomedical data appears to be a very promising approach [6, 7].

In WHO therapeutic schemes for malaria treatment, 11 antimalarial drugs are natural products or their analogues or were design-based on the pharmacophores from natural products [8]. Traditional medicines continue to be natural, cheaper and most affordable means of treatment methods for malaria and they have also proven to be a source of major drug lead for synthetic counterpart. Therefore this review focuses on medicinal plants used in traditional medicine in the treatment of malaria infections in some countries of the community of Africa, which includes Nigeria, Cameroon, Ghana, Kenya, Mali, Tanzania, Uganda, and involved the comparison of popularly used antimalarial activity of extracts and isolated substances and may be some of these plant metabolites could be used as templates for designing new derivatives with improved properties.

Traditional Treatment of Malaria

The use of traditional antimalarial drug plays an important role in daily health care in Africa, herbal remedies are even preferred to modern medicines in both urban and rural areas of Africa community. Traditional antimalarial drugs are commonly sold in markets and public places or administered by healers in traditional clinics [9, 10] Whole plants or parts of them are prepared and administered as oral decoction, steam baths, infusion or enema. Most remedies are a concoction of two or more plant species and solvents used include water, palm wine or oils [11].

Africa has as much as three hundred thousand medicinal plants, [12], approximately 80% of population in Africa use traditional medicines in primary health care, including 40,000-70,000 medicinal plants, approximately 20% of all higher-plant species [13].

For many years, traditional medicine has proven to be the surest source of effective antimalarial, the alkaloid quinine was extracted from the bark of cinchona, and this was the first antimalarial drug used by the inhabitants of Peru to control malaria. Three other antimalarial compounds, namely, quinidine, cinchonine, and cinchonidine had also been isolated from this plant. [14] Quinine served as a lead structure for the synthesis of several antimalarial drugs such as chloroquine, mefloquine, pyrimethamine, proguanil, atovaquone (sold together with proguanil as “Malarone”), or primaquine. Quinine (alone or in combination with doxycycline, tetracycline or clindamycin) is still used today to treat acute cases of severe *P. falciparum* infections [15]. Another plant-based antimalarial drug isolated from the Chinese plant *Artemisia annua* in seventies [16]. World Health Organization recommended the use of artemisin in based combination therapy (ACT) for the treatment of uncomplicated malaria in endemic regions of the world since ACT greatly reduced the morbidity and mortality due to acute severe malaria in endemic Africa countries [17]. Currently available ACT has some limitations which include high cost beyond what the average African rural dweller can afford, unavailability of the raw materials and toxicity [18]. Clinical resistance to these combinations has been recently reported in Cambodia [19], suggesting that *P. falciparum* parasites have already developed the ability to grow in the presence of these antimalarials, which strongly suggests the need for further research into new antimalarials.

African Medicinal Plants for Malaria Treatment

African traditional treatment of malaria is a comprehensive knowledge system, which comprises the utilization of herbal drugs, dosages and practices based on socio-cultural norms, and religious belief as well as witnessed experience and observation of a specific group [20]. The knowledge of treatment of malaria with herbal medicines in Africa is currently transmitted from one generation to another principally by verbal medium without concise documentation; therefore there is availability of only minute documented information about traditional herbal medicine in Africa [21].

In various African countries, several plants have been reported to be having antimalarial effects and are being applied traditionally as antimalarial agents. A wide variety of plants illustrated in table 1 found in African nations, belonging to several families have been identified through ethnobotanical and ethnopharmacological studies as antimalarial medicinal plants [4, 9, 11, 21-25].

Table 1: Indigenous medicinal plants used for malaria treatment in Africa

No	Plants	Parts	Common names	Preparations	Countries
1	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Bulbs	Garlic	Decoction	Cameroon, Nigeria, Uganda Ivory coast, Nigeria
2	<i>Alstoniaboonei</i>	Leaves, root, stem barks	Stool wood	Decoction	Kenya
3	<i>Ajugaremota</i>	Leaves	Ajuga	Decoction	Burundi, Nigeria
4	<i>Artemisia annua</i>	Leaves, seeds	Sweet wormwood	Decoction	Nigeria
5	<i>Aspiilia africana</i>	Stem barks	Wild sun flower	Decoction	Nigeria
6	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Barks, leaves	Dogoyanro, neem	Decoction,	

7	<i>Bridelia ferruginea</i>	Barks, leaves, roots Leaves, roots	Mitzeerie Pigeon pea	infusion Decoction	Nigeria, Ghana, Tanzania, Uganda Nigeria, Togo
8	<i>Cajanus cajan</i>			Decoction	
9	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Leaves, fruits, roots Barks	Paw paw African bark	Decoction, infusion	Cameroon, Nigeria, Uganda Burkina Faso, Ghana,
10	<i>Crossopteryx febrifuga</i>	Leaves Whole plant, root	Lemon grass	Decoction	Central Africa Cameroon, Nigeria
11	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>		Hairy spurge	Decoction	
12	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	Barks, leaves		Decoction	Ivory coast, Cameroon, Togo
13	<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	Barks Leaves	Bitter kola	Decoction	Cameroon, Nigeria Nigeria
14	<i>Garcinia kola</i>	Stem barks	Easter tree	Decoction	Kenya
15	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>		Mahogany	Decoction	
16	<i>Khaya grandifoliola</i>	Leaves, stem barks, roots	African mahogany	Decoction, infusion	Cameroon, Nigeria
17	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Barks, leaves	Mango	Decoction, infusion	Cameroon, Nigeria
18	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Barks, leaves, roots Leaves, stem bark, root	Brimstone tree	Decoction	Cameroon, Ghana, Uganda
19	<i>Morindalucida</i>	Leaves, roots	Moringa	Decoction, tincture	Ghana, Nigeria
20	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>		African peach	Decoction	Ghana, Uganda
21	<i>Nuclea latifolia</i>	Leaves	Tea bush Opilia	Decoction	Ghana, Nigeria Nigeria, Uganda
22	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	Leaves, stem barks, roots,		Decoction	
23	<i>Opilia celtidifolia</i>	Barks, leaves	African locust bean tree	Decoction	Burkina Faso, Togo, Cameroon, Ghana, Nigeria
24	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>		Guava	Decoction	Cameroon, Nigeria
25	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Leaves	Bitter wood	Decoction	Nigeria
26	<i>Quassia amara</i>	Leaves, stem barks, roots Aerial parts	Serpent wood	Decoction	Nigeria
27	<i>Rauvolfia vomitoria</i>		Broom weed	Infusion	Kenya, Ivory coast, Nigeria
28	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Leaves	Bitter leaf	Decoction	Ghana, Nigeria, Tanzania, Uganda
29	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Leaves, roots	Ginger	Decoction, infusion	Cameroon, Nigeria
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>			Decoction	

The next generation of antimalarial may be found in plants currently used in Africa, artemisinin has been discovered in Asia, Latin American has offered quinine to humanity. Many researchers believe that it is Africa's turn to offer a new antimalarial drug to humanity [26].

Figure 1, indicates the medicinal plants employed as antimalarial in Africa as a promising source for the development of new and better antimalarial drugs. This is however very important due to the current urgent need for novel antimalarial drug development so as to curtail the challenges being faced currently in the treatment/control of malaria [27].

Figure 1: Medicinal plants used to treat malaria in Africa

A= *Allium sativa*; B=*Azadirachta indica*; C= *Carica papaya* ; D=*Parkia biglobosa*

Preparation of Plant materials

Traditional antimalarial drugs may be collected from wild or cultivated plants, it is known that the active constituents of medicinal plants are affected by many factors such as time of the year, time of the day, stage of maturity and age and these may vary during the course of plant growth. Proper time of collection is very important to obtain a drug of good quality [28]. Identification of plant material is the key to all following steps in antimalarial natural products isolation, in the medicinal plant area the awareness of necessity of authentication of biological material has been given a boost by significantly increasing emergence of herbal drugs from traditional medicine [29]. The method of identification involves keeping of the track of investigated material of each study, a voucher specimen is kept locally and also stored in a major herbarium [30]. Other steps are as pre-washing, drying of plant materials or freeze drying, grinding to obtain a homogenous sample and often improving the kinetics of analytic extraction and also increasing the contact of sample surface with the solvent system [31].

Extraction of Plant materials

Extraction is the crucial first step in the analysis of medicinal plants, the desired chemical components from the plant materials must be extracted for further separation and characterization. The potential active constituents must not be lost, distorted or destroyed during the preparation of the extract from plant samples therefore proper actions must be taken. If necessary, the method of preparation of extract by the traditional healer may be replicated in order to mimic as closely as possible the traditional antimalarial herbal drug [31].

The extraction of the compounds depends on the specific nature of the bioactive compound being targeted, these include the polarity, stability of the extractives and the solvents, the toxicity, volatility and purity of the extraction solvent, the probability of artefact formation during extraction process and the amount of bulk material to be extracted. Hydrophilic antimalarial compounds are extracted with polar solvents such as methanol, ethanol or ethyl-acetate, dichloromethane or a mixture of dichloromethane/methanol in ratio of 1:1 are used for extraction of lipophilic compounds. In some instances, extraction with hexane is used to remove chlorophyll [32]. The various methods of extraction for non-polar to polar and thermally labile are maceration, percolation, soxhlet extraction, ultrasound assisted extraction and turbo extraction [30]. The filtrate is concentrated by rotary evaporation to obtain the crude extract, the extract is then tested in various systems mainly *in vitro* incubation with *Plasmodium* parasite or *in vivo* in a malaria animal model. It is worth mentioning that several *Plasmodium falciparum* strains, which have been successfully adapted to *in vitro* culture, are employed in testing, while a number of animal and human models are also used for *in vivo* studies [33]. Several extracts derived from plants used as African traditional antimalarial [9, 33-41) are illustrated in Table 2

Table 2: Antimalarial activities and toxicities of indigenous medicinal plant extracts

No.	Plants	Extracts	In vivo (%)	In vitro (µg/ml)	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg)
1	<i>Allium sativum</i>	AQ	-	0.5	3034
2	<i>Alstonia bonnei</i>	AQ, EOH	66.4, 100	0.2, 3.2,	>5000
3	<i>Ajuga remota</i>	CHCL, MOH, H ₂ O	77.5	22.1, > 100	>2000
4	<i>Artemisia annua</i>	AQ, HOH, HX	52.8, 94.3	3.27,4.95	2750
5	<i>Aspilia africana</i>	AQ, EOH, MOH	92.2	9.3,22.7	894
6	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	AQ, EA, EOH	79.6	2.50, 11.5	6200
7	<i>Bridelia ferruginea</i>	AQ	95	-	> 5000
8	<i>Cajanus cajan</i>	DM, EA, EOH	40.0	15.6, 31.3	>3000
9	<i>Carica papaya</i>	PE, MOH	100	15.2, 16.8	2000
10	<i>Crossopteryx febrifuga</i>	CHCL, EOH	84.7	>10	774
11	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	DM, EA, PE	87.2	9.1, 12.1	2500
12	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	EOH, MOH	59.1	4.33, 10.7	3800
13	<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	EOH, PE	43.5	13.8, 15.3	3800
14	<i>Garnicia kola</i>	CHCL, MOH	-	1.6, 2.9	358
15	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	HX, MOH, MCD	43.0	5.7, 28	2000
16	<i>Khaya grandifoliola</i>	MOH	>80	0.84, 1.40,	5500
17	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	EOH	< 80	<5.00	>3000
18	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	DM, EOH	67.7,100	14.0, 24.3	18400
19	<i>Morinda lucida</i>	PE, MCD, MOH	55.0	3.9, 5.2	5000
20	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	EOH	100	15.1	6617.00
21	<i>Nuclea latifolia</i>	AQ, DM	63.8	0.60	1183
22	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	AQ, MOH	88.0	1.84	4240
23	<i>Opilia celtidifolia</i>	AQ, DM	-	2.8	636

24	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	AQ	55.6, 100	12.9, 56.2	>5000
25	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	EOH	<80	6.0	> 5000
26	<i>Quassia amara</i>	EOH, H ₂ O	-	8.9	>2000
27	<i>Rauvolfia vomitoria</i>	EA, DM	-	1.0, 2.5	> 5000
28	<i>Sida acuta</i>	AQ, MOH	-	0.92, 3.90	3400
29	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	MOH	97.8	4.1	>5000
30	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	AQ, EOH	<60	15.9	5000

AQ: Aqueous, CHCL: Chloroform, DM: Dichloromethane, EOH: Ethanol, EA: Ethyl acetate, HX: Hexane, HOH: Hydro alcoholic : MOH: Methanol, PE: Petroleum ether, H₂O : Water

Identification and Characterization of Active antimalarial compounds

Antimalarial plant extracts usually occur as a combination of various types of bioactive compounds or phytochemicals with different polarities, therefore the separation of active antimalarial compounds still remains a big challenge for the process of identification and characterization. A number of different separation techniques such as TLC, column chromatography, flash chromatography, Sephadex chromatography and HPLC, are used to obtain pure compounds. The pure compounds are then used for the determination of structure and biological activity. Also non-chromatographic techniques such as phytochemical screening assay, Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), can also be used to obtain and facilitate the identification of the bioactive antimalarial compounds [29].

Thin layer chromatography (TLC) is a simple, quick, and inexpensive procedure, this is used to determine the number of components in a mixture. TLC is also used to support the identity of a compound in a mixture when the R_f of a compound is compared with the R_f of a known compound. Other tests such as spraying of phytochemical screening reagents, which cause colour changes according to the phytochemicals existing in a plants extract; or viewing the plate under the UV light can also be carried out. This has also been used for confirmation of purity and identity of isolated antimalarial compounds [29].

Another widely used technique for the isolation of natural antimalarial products is High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). Currently, this technique is an analytical technique for fingerprinting study for the quality control of herbal antimalarial plants [29]. Natural products are frequently isolated following the evaluation of a relatively crude extract in a biological assay in order to fully characterize the active entity. The biologically active entity is often present only as minor component in the extract and the resolving power of HPLC is ideally suited to the rapid processing of such multicomponent samples on both an analytical and preparative scale [42].

Non-chromatographic techniques such as Immunoassays, which use monoclonal antibodies (MAbs) against drugs and low molecular weight natural bioactive antimalarial compounds, are becoming important tools in bioactive compound analyses. They show high specificity and sensitivity for receptor binding analyses, enzyme assays and qualitative as well as quantitative analytical techniques. Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) based on MAbs are in many cases more sensitive than conventional HPLC methods [43].

Phytochemical Screening Assays

Phytochemicals are large number of secondary metabolic compounds found in plants, these are chemically obtained from plant. Phytochemical screening assay is a simple, quick, and inexpensive procedure and is used for the determination of the various types of secondary metabolites in a mixture and an important tool in bioactive compound analyses. After obtaining the crude extract or active fraction from plant material, phytochemical

screening can be performed with the appropriate tests as indicated in the Table 3 to get an idea regarding the type of phytochemicals existing in extract mixture or fraction [29].

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) is a valuable technique for the characterization and identification of compounds or functional groups (chemical bonds) present in an unknown mixture of antimalarial plants extract [44]. Also FTIR spectra of pure compounds are usually so unique that they are like a molecular "fingerprint". For most common antimalarial plant compounds, the spectrum of an unknown compound can be identified by comparison to a library of known compounds [29].

A large number of antimalarial compounds with a wide variety of structures have been isolated from plants and can play a role in the development of new antimalarial drugs. The pure product is further tested for antimalarial activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* [34-35, 39-40, 45-48] as mentioned below as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Antimalarial activity and cytotoxicity of phytochemicals from African indigenous plants

No	Plants	Phytochemicals	<i>In vivo</i> (%)	<i>In vitro</i> (µg/ml)	Cytotoxicity (µg/ml)
1	<i>Allium sativum</i>	Ajoene, alliacin	94.0,100.0	-	100
2	<i>Ajugaremota</i>	Ajugarin-1	-	23.0	-
3	<i>Artemisia annua</i>	Artemisinin	100	1.00, 5.10	28.3
4	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Gedunin	-	0.020, 0.039	2.300
5	<i>Cajanuscajan</i>	Cajachalcone	-	2.00	<50
6	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Terpenoids, aldehyde	-	4-10	>2000
7	<i>Garnicia kola</i>	Kolaviron	92.6	-	<1500
8	<i>Khayagrandifoliola</i>	Gedunin	-	1.25	21.6, 37.6
9	<i>Khayasenegalensis</i>	2,6-dihydroxyfissinolide Saponins, tannins	-	0.120	61.1
10	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Urosilic acid	-	20	15-30
11	<i>Morinda lucida</i>	TOG 1-7	-	3.1	>2000
12	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	Phenol	-	0.32-0.52	>2000
13	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Similikalactone D, E	100	0.51	-
14	<i>Quassia amara</i>	Cryptolepines	-	0.010-0.068	22.6
15	<i>Sida acuta</i>		-	0.13,0.17	9.000
16	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Sesquiterpene lactones	-	< 4.0	>1000

Toxicity of African traditional antimalarial drugs

Clinical studies conducted to validate the efficacy and safety of African traditional antimalarial are few [29, 49] studies have shown that some African traditional antimalarial may produce low rates of parasite clearance but higher rates of adequate clinical response [50]. Information on the toxicity of African indigenous antimalarial is provided in

table 2, the Lethal Dose (LD₅₀) values are required to predict the safety associated before the use of these herbal antimalarial [25, 51-75]. A number of cases of toxicity were reported by patients taking herbal antimalarial, minor side effects such as diarrhoea, bitter taste were observed with many herbal preparations. Literature review has revealed that many African indigenous antimalarials displayed significant cytotoxic effects [48, 76- 80] on mammalian cells as shown in table 3, therefore screening for inhibitors against parasite-specific targets in organelles like the apicoplast and pathways such as heme degradation and type II fatty acid biosynthesis is recommended to identify active leads with highly selective antiplasmodial action so that reliable quality controls can be established.[26, 50].

Conclusion

African traditional knowledge and medications play a large role in primary healthcare, rural and urban setting, however African indigenous antimalarials are not without drawbacks. Lack of clinical studies on safety and efficacy, poor toxicological data, concentration and seasonal variation of active ingredients, conservation of biodiversity, problems with plant species, patent and inadequate standardized preparations and dosages reduce the interest of large funding organization in African tradition medicine. Indigenous medicinal plants in many of these African countries used in combating malaria are yet to be projected in conferences as the foreign plants in spite of our rich flora diversity, it is essential to establish the efficacy and safety of African indigenous antimalarials which are used to fight the malaria. Therefore, it is hope that some of these active compounds generated from rich Africa flora will replace and control drug-resistant *P. falciparum* parasites in regions where ACT is less effective.

References

1. Fidock DA, Rosenthal PJ, Croft SL, Brun R, Nwaka S. Antimalarial drug discovery: efficacy models for compound screening. *Nat. rev. /Drug Disc*, 2004, 3: 509-520.
2. Rathod PK, Mcertean T, Pei-cheich L. Variations in frequencies of drug resistance in *Plasmodium falciparum*. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of United States of America*, 1997, 94: 9389 – 9393.
3. Benjamin K, Koram KK, Binta FN. Antimalarial drug use among caregivers in Ghana. *Afr Hlt Sci*, 2004, 4: 3.
4. Zirihi GN, Mambu L, Guede-Guina F, Bodo B, Grellier P. *In vitro* antiplasmodial activity and cytotoxicity of 33 West African plants used for treatment of malaria. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2005, 98:281-285.
5. Ridley RG. Medical need, scientific opportunity and the drive for antimalarial drugs. *Nature*, 2002, 415:686-693.
6. Newman DJ. Natural products as leads to potential drugs: an old process or the new hope for drug discovery? *J Med Chem*, 2008, 51: 2589-2599.
7. Turschner S, Efferth T. Drug resistance in Plasmodium: natural products in the fight against malaria. *Mini Rev Med Chem*, 2009, 9: 2006-2124.
8. Bourdy G, Willcox ML, Ginsburg H, Rasoanaivo P, Graz B, Deharo E. Ethnopharmacology and malaria: new hypothetical leads or old efficient antimalarials? *Int J Parasitol*, 2008, 38: 33-41.
9. Abubakar FA, Adetutu A, Olorunnisola OS. Ethnobotanical survey and antiplasmodial screening of commonly used plants in the treatment of malaria in Ilorin metropolis. *Int J Phytofuels Allied sci*, 2015, 4: 13-30.
10. Nordeng H, Al-Zayadi W, Diallo D, Ballo N, Paulsen BS. Traditional medicine practitioners' knowledge and views on treatment of pregnant women in three regions of Mali. *J Ethnobiol Ethnomed*, 2013, 9: 1-9.
11. Gronhaug TE, Glaeserud S, Skogsrud M, Ballo N, Bah S, Diallo D, Paulsen BS. Ethnopharmacological survey of six medicinal plants from Mali. *West Afr J Ethnobiol Ethnomed*, 2008, 4: 1746-1842.
12. Sofowora EA. Medicinal Plants and Traditional Medicine in Africa. Wiley, New York, 1982.
13. Verpoorte R, Kim HK, Choi YH. Plants as source of medicines. In RJ Bogers, LE Craker, D Lange, Medicinal and aromatic plants, Springer, Netherlands, 2006: 261-273.

14. Willcox M. Improved traditional phytomedicines in current use for the clinical treatment of malaria. *Planta Med*, 2011, 77: 662–671.
15. Michael W. Medicinal plants; A source of antiparasitic secondary metabolites. *Mol*, 2012, 17: 12771-12791.
16. Klayman DL. Qinghaosu (artemisinin): an antimalarial drug from China. *Sci*, 1985, 228: 1049-1055.
17. Mokuolu OA, Okoro EO, Ayetoro SO, Adewara AA. Effect of artemisinin based treatment policy on consumption pattern of antimalarial. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2007, 105: 131-136.
18. Balogun EA, Adebayo JO, Ademowo, OG. Activity of ethanolic extract of *Clerodend rumviolaceum* leaves against plasmodium berghei in mice. *Agric Bio J*, 2009, 3: 307 – 312.
19. Noedl H, Se Y, Schaecher K, Smith BL, Socheat D, Fukuda MM. Evidence of artemisinin-resistant malaria in western Cambodia. *N Engl J Med*, 2008, 359: 2619-2620.
20. Diallo D, Paulsen BS. Pharmaceutical research and traditional practitioners in Mali: Experiences with benefit sharing. In *Responding to bioprospecting (From biodiversity in the South to medicines in the North)* Edited by: Svarstad H, Dhillon SS. Oslo: Spartacus Forlag; 2000:133-144.
21. Chinedu E, Arome D, Ameh SF. African Herbal Plants used as Anti-Malarial Agents - A Review. *Pharma Tutor*, 2014, 2: 47-53.
22. Odugbemi TO, Akinsulire OR, Aibinu IE, Fabeku PO. Medicinal Plants Useful for Malaria Therapy in Okeigbo, Ondo State, Southwest Nigeria. *Afr J Trad CAM*, 2007, 4: 191- 198.
23. Tabuti JS. Herbal medicines used in the treatment of malaria in Budiope County, Uganda. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2008, 116: 33–42.
24. Asase A, Oteng-Yeboah AA, Odamten GT, Simmonds MS. Ethnobotanical study of some Ghanaian anti-malarial plants. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2005; 273–279.
25. Builders MI. *Parkia biglobosa* (African Locust Bean Tree), *World J Pharmaceut Res*, 2014, 3: 1672-1682.
26. Amoa Onguéné P, Ntie-Kang F, Lifongo LL, Ndom JC, Sippl W, Mbaze LM. The potential of anti-malarial compounds derived from African medicinal plants, part I: A pharmacological evaluation of alkaloids and terpenoids. *Malar J*, 2013, 12:449.
27. Randrianarivelojosia M, Rasidimanana V T, Rabarison H, Cheplogoi P K, Ratsimbason M, Mulholland D A and Mauclère P. Plants traditionally prescribed to treat tazo (malaria) in the eastern region of Madagascar. *Malar J*, 2003, 2.
28. World Health Organization (WHO). Traditional Medicine Strategy: 2002-2005. Geneva, World Health Organization, 2002 (document WHO/EDM/TRM/2002.1)
29. Sasidharan S, Chen Y, Saravanan D, Sundram KM, Latha LY. Extraction, isolation and characterization of bioactive compounds from plants' extracts. *Afr J Trad CAM*, 2011, 8:1-10.
30. Bucar F, Wube A, Schmid M. Natural product isolation-how to get from biological material to pure compound. *Nat Prod Rep*, 2013, 30; 525-545.
31. Fabricant, DS, Farnsworth NR. The value of plants used in traditional medicine for drug discovery. *Environ Hlt Perspect*, 2001, 109: 69–75.
32. Cosa, P, Vlietinck, AJ, Berghe DV, Maes L. Anti-infective potential of natural products: How to develop a stronger *in vitro* 'proof-of-concept'. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2006, 106: 290–302.
33. Jeruto P, Nyangacha RM, Mutai C. *In vitro* and *in vivo* antiplasmodial activity of extracts of selected Kenyan medicinal plants. *Afr J Pharm Pharmacol*, 2015, 9: 500-505.
34. Titanji PV, Zofou D, Ngemenya MN. The antimalarial potential of medicinal plants used for the treatment of malaria in Cameroonian folk medicine. *Afr J Trad CAM*, 2008, 5: 302 - 321.
35. Lawal B, Shittu OK, Kabiru AY, Jigam AA, Umar MB, Berinyuy EB, Alozieuwa BU. Potential antimalarials from African natural products: A review. *J Intercult Ethnopharmacol*, 2015, 4: 318-343.
36. Adebayo JO, Krettli AU. Potential antimalarials from Nigerian plants: A review. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2011, 133:289-302.
37. Builders M.I (2015). Plants as antimalarial drugs: A review. *W J Pharm Pharmaceut Sci* 8, 1747-1766.

38. Ogbole EA, Idyu I, Ogundeko T, Asalu AF, Builders M, Aguiyi J. Acute toxicity studies of locally cultivated *Artemisia annua* leaf extract in rats. *World J Pharmaceut sci*, 2014, 2: 1864-1870.
39. Jeje TO, Ibraheem O, Brai BC, Ibukun EO. Pharmacological potential of asthma weed (*Euphorbia hirta*) extract toward eradication of *Plasmodium berghei* in infected albino mice. *Int J Toxicolog Pharmacolog Res*, 2016, 8: 130-137.
40. Dike P, Obembe OO, Adebisi FE. Ethnobotanical survey for potential antimalarial plants in South Western Nigeria. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2012, 10: 1-9.
41. Ibrahim HA, Imam IA, Bello AM, Umar U, Muhammad S, Abdullahi SA. The potential of Nigerian medicinal plants as antimalarial Agent: A Review. *Int J Sci Technolog*, 2012, 2:600-605.
42. Fan XH, Cheng YY, Ye ZL, Lin RC, Qian ZZ. Multiple chromatographic fingerprinting and its application to the quality control of herbal medicines. *Anal Chim. Acta*, 2006, 555: 217-224.
43. Shoyama Y, Tanaka H, Fukuda N. Monoclonal antibodies against naturally occurring bioactive compounds. *Cytotechnol*, 2003, 31: 9-27.
44. Hazra KM, Roy RN, Sen SK, Laska S. Isolation of antibacterial pentahydroxy flavones from the seeds of *Mimusopselengi* Linn. *Afr J Biotechnol*, 2007, 6: 1446-1449.
45. Chinsambu KA. Plants as antimalarial agents in sub-saharan Africa. *Acta tropica*, 2015, 150: 32-48.
46. Zime-Diawara H, Ganfon H, Gbaguidi F, Yemoa A, Bero J, Jansen O, Evrard B, Moudachirou M, Frederich M, Quetin-Leclercq J. The antimalarial action of aqueous and hydro alcoholic extracts of *Artemisia annua* L. cultivated in Benin: *In vitro* and *in vivo* studies. *J Chem Pharma Res*, 2015, 7:817-823.
47. Builders MI, Alemika T, Aguiyi JC. Antimalarial activity and isolation of phenolic compounds from *Parkia biglobosa*, *IOSRJ PharmBiolog Sci*, 2014, 9: 78-85.
48. Abiodun O, Gbotosho G, Ajaiyeoba E, Happi T, Falade M, Wittlin S, Sowunmi A, Brun R, Oduola A. *In vitro* antiplasmodial activity and toxicity assessment of some plants from Nigerian ethnomedicine. *Pharmaceut Biolog*, 2011, 49: 9-14.
49. Ngarivhume T, Klooster C, Jong J, Westuizen J. Medicinal plants used by traditional healers for the treatment of malaria in Chinpinge district in Zimbabwe. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 2015, 159: 224-237.
50. Willcox ML, Bodeker G. Traditional herbal medicines for malaria. *BMJ*, 2004, 329:1156-1159.
51. Chanda S, Parekh J, Vaghasiya Y, Dave R, Baravalia Y, Nair R. Medicinal plants - from traditional use to toxicity assessment: a review. *IJPSR*, 2015, 6: 2652-2670.
52. Mikai HG. Phytochemical screening, elemental analysis and acute toxicity of aqueous extract of *Allium sativum* L. bulbs in experimental rabbits. *J MedPlt Res*, 2010, 4: 322-326.
53. NkonoYaNkono BL, Sokeng SD, Dzeufiet Djomeni PD, Kamtchouing P. Antihyperglycemic and antioxydant properties of *Alstoniaboonei* De Wild. (Apocynaceae) stem bark aqueous extract in dexamethasone-induced hyperglycemic rats. *Int J Diabetes Res*, 2014, 3: 27-35.
54. Nardos A, Makonnen E. *In vivo* antiplasmodial activity and toxicological assessment of hydroethanolic crude extract of *Ajugaremota*. *Malar J*, 2017, 16:25.
55. Okoli CC, Akah PA, Okoli AS. Potentials of leaves of *Aspilia africana* (Compositae) in wound care: an experimental evaluation. *BMC CAM*, 2007, 7: 1-7.
56. Bark A. Evaluation of acute toxicity of water extract of *Azadirachta indica* leaves and seeds in rats. *Pakistan J Biolog Sci*, 2013, 16: 697-700.
57. Olusi TA, Ibukunoluwa MB, Dada O. Nutritional quality assessment and antiplasmodial activity of *Cajanus cajan* (L) Huth, *Crescentia cujete* L and *Myrianthus preussi*, Engl from Akure. *Int J Phytomed*, 2015, 7: 449-458.
58. Halim SZ, Abdullah NR, Afzan A, Abdul Rashid BA, Jantan I, Ismail Z. Acute toxicity study of *Carica papaya* leaf extract in Sprague Dawley rats. *J Med Plt Res*, 2011, 5: 1867-1872.
59. Salawu AO, Tijani YA, Akingbasote JA, Oga E F. Acute and subacute toxicity study of ethanolic extract of the stem bark of *Faidherbia albida* (DEL) A. chev (Mimosoidae) in rats. *Afr J Biotechnol*, 2010, 8: 1218-1224.

60. Dafam DG, Kagaru DC, Ajima U, Ezekwu P1, Falang K. D. Anti-inflammatory and toxicity studies of the ethanolic extract of the leaves of *Ficus platyplla* Del (Moraceae) *J Chem Pharmaceut Res*, 2014, 6:5-9 .
61. Kagbo H, Ejebe D. Phytochemistry and preliminary toxicity studies of the methanol extract of the stem bark of *Garcinia kola* (Heckel). *The Int J Toxicol*, 2009, 7: 1-8.
62. Saha S, Subrahmanyam EV. Evaluation of anti-inflammatory activity of ethanolic extract of seeds of *Holarrhena pubescens* (buch.- ham.) wall. *Int J Pharm Pharmaceut Sci* , 2013, 5: 915-919.
63. Njikam RN, Njikam N. Curative Dose of *Khaya grandifoliola* stem bark for the treatment of gastric ulcers using wistar rats. *Pharmaceut Biolog*, 2006, 44: 152-155.
64. Nwosu CU, Hassan SW, Abubakar MG, Ebbo AA. Antidiarrhoeal and toxicological studies of leaf extract of *Khaya senegalensis*. *J Pharm Toxicol*, 2012, 1-10.
65. Zhang Y, Jian L, Wu Z, Liu E, Shi P, Han L, Guo L, Gao X, Wang T. Acute and long-term toxicity of mango leaves extract in mice and rats. *Evid Based CAM*, 2014, 691574:1- 8 .
66. Adejo GO, Akintayo CO, Obinna M. *Morinda lucida* leaf and fruit extracts may attenuate diarrhea arising from ebola. *Basic Res J Med Clin Sci*, 2015, 4: 95-100.
67. Osman HM, Shayoub ME, Babiker EM, Faiza AO, Munzir ME, Osman AB, Mohamed A, Taha KK. Assessment of acute toxicity and LD₅₀ of *Moringa oleifera* ethanolic leaf extract in albino rats and rabbits. *J Med Biolog Sci Res*, 2015, 1: 38 – 43.
68. Ojo OA, Oloyede OI, Olarewaju OI, Ojo AB, Ajiboye BO, Onikanni SA. Toxicity Studies of the crude aqueous leaves extracts of *Ocimum gratissimum* in albino rats. *IOSR J EnvironSci Toxicol Food Technol*, 2013, 6: 34-39.
69. Jaiarj P, Khoohaswan P, Wongkrajang Y, Peungvicha P, Suriyawong P, Saraya ML, Ruangsomboon O. Anticough and antimicrobial activities of *Psidium guajava* Linn. Leaf extract. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 1999, 67; 203-215.
70. Arantes VP, Emerick GL, Fernandes LS, Pereira IO, DeOliveira GH. Preclinical toxicity evaluation of *Quassia amara* extract with potential antimycobacterial activity. *J Bioanal Biomed*, 2012, 1-6.
71. Akouah L, N'douaa R, Abob K, Aoussic S, Kouakoud LK, Ehilee EE. Aqueous extract of *Rauwolfia vomitoria* Afzel (Apocynaceae) roots effect on blood glucose level of normoglycemic and hyperglycemic rats. *Am Sci Res J Enginee TechnolSci*, 2016, 20: 66-77.
72. Konate K, Bassole IH, Hilou A, Samseny AR, Souza A, Dicko MH, Datte JY, Batchi BM. Toxicity assessment and analgesic activity investigation of aqueous acetone extracts of *Sida acuta* Burn f. and *Sida cordifolia* L. (Malvaceae), medicinal plants of Burkina Faso. *BMCCAM*, 2012, 12:120.
73. Yeap SK, Liang WS, BehBK, HoWY, Yousr AN, Alitheen NB. *In vivo* antidiabetic and acute toxicity of spray-dried *Vernonia amygdalina* water extract. *Int Food Res J*, 2013, 20: 613-616.
74. Attah AH, Eilkoy TA, Mouneir SM, Kamel G, Alwabel NA, Zahel S. Hepatoprotective effect of methanol extracts of *Zingiber officinale* and *Cichorium intybus*. *Indian J Pharm Sci*, 2010, 72: 564–570.
75. Ogbole EA, Ogbole Y, Peter JY, Builders MI, Aguiyi, JC. Phytochemical screening and *in vivo* antiplasmodial sensitivity study of locally cultivated *Artemisia annua* leaf extract against *Plasmodium berghei*. *Am J Ethnomed*, 2014, 1: 042-049.
76. Sanon S, Adama G, Lamoussa PO, Abdoulaye T, Issa NO, Alfred T, et alxxx. *In vitro* antiplasmodial and cytotoxic properties of some medicinal plants from western Burkina Faso. *Afr J Lab Med*, 2013, 2:1-7.
77. Prakash E, Saxena AK, Gupta DK. Cytotoxic activities of ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* against colon cancer cell lines. *Int J Innovative Res Sci, Engineer Technol*, 2016, 5:3.
78. Singh NP, Ferreira JS, Park JS, Lai HC. Cytotoxicity of ethanolic extracts of *Artemisia annua* to molt-4 human leukemia cells. *Planta Med*, 2011, 77: 1788–1793.
79. Souda SS, Aboutab EA, Maamoun AA, Hashem FA. Volatile constituents and cytotoxic activity of *Khaya grandifoliola* and *Khaya senegalensis* flower extracts. *J Herb SpicesMed plant*, 2016, 22 : 183-189.

80. Abdullah AS, Mohammed SA, Abdullah R, Mirghani ME, Al-Qubaisi M. Cytotoxic effect of *Mangifera indica* L kernel extract on human breast cancer (MCE-7 and MDA-MB-231 cell lines) and bioactive constituents in the crude extract. *BMC CAM*, 2014, 14: 199, 1-10.

